

Appendix I. Variables, questions and items of the questionnaire used.

López, P., Serrano, J.L. & Gutiérrez, I. (2022). Personal Management of Digital Information in University Students from a Gender Perspective. New Approaches in Educational Research.

Information management processes	Questionnaire question	Items
Information search	Nº13. When I want to learn something new I go to:	Colleagues and friends face to face
		Online communication media
		Blogs or websites
		Wikipedia or online encyclopedias
		Social Networks
		Forums
		Online video tutorials or slides
		Mobile applications specific to the subject
	Nº14. When I search for information I uses:	Colleagues and friends contacting them by email or private messages
		A single general search engine
		Various general search engines
		Specialized heme search engines
		Specific theme search engines
		Libraries and online databases
	Nº15. To access information I make	Social networks
Debate forums		
Exploratory searches in manuals, textbooks, encyclopedias		
Exploratory searches with web engines		
Systematic searches in specialist journals		
Information selection	Nº 22. From the information I locate, I select:	Searches of specific databases
		Searches of specialized websites and portals
		Searches by authors of reference
		That which is aesthetically most appealing
		The most up-to-date
		That which is expressed in the most simple language
		That in audiovisual format
	Nº 17. When working with information, for better understanding I prefer it to be:	That which starts from a clear idea
		The most recommended
		That which it is compulsory I revise
		Iconic (photographs or pictures)
	Nº 19. I question the information I receive from:	Video
		Audio
		Multimedia
		Hypermedia
My teachers		
Friends and family		
Traditional communication media		
Network communication means		
Blogs and websites		
Twitter		
Social networks		
Nº 20. What adds credibility to the information I receive?	Forums	
	Tutorials	
	Specific mobile applications	
	News in my emails	
	Experts or professionals in the field	
	Recommended by colleagues, friends and family	
	Recommended on social networks	
Its appearance in an online recommendation system (“meneame”, “tripadvisor”)		
A top spot on google		
A trending topic on twitter		
Its appearance in several online resources (articles, books, videos)		
Recommended by an expert		

Organization of information	Nº 25. When organizing and managing information I prefer to	Organize it in folders (hierarchies)
		Organize it in a timeline
		Use social markers
		Use Wikis / Use Blogs
		Use a social network tool
	Nº 24. I usually save information:	In my computer and on Internet (the cloud)
Information processing	Nº 26. What do I do with my notes and important information I find?	I store it carefully
		I make a diagram/ mind map to relate it: on paper, in a text document, /in a specific online tool
		I summarize it: on paper/in a text document /with an entry on my personal page /with an entry that I share on a social network
	Nº 27. When I find and interesting document:	I read it online and take notes using a specific online tool (diigo or similar)
		I include it in a specific management tool (mendeley, RefWorks or similar) and take notes on it in that tool
		I download the document to my computer and take notes with a specific tool as I read it on the screen.
		I use metadata to incorporate it into my own resources
	Nº 28. When I find a video or audi that interests me:	I print it, underline and make notes on the paper and then put the notes in a text document and save them
		I listen to it/watch it online and take handwritten notes
		I listen to it/watch it online and take notes in a text document
	Nº 29. When I receive new information that interests me:	I listen to it/watch it online and take notes using a specially designed program
		I analyze it
		I interpret it
		I relate it to what I know
		I compare it with what I know
I get questions / doubts		
Creation of the information	Nº 31. When I use information from others I do it:	I try to check it against other sources
		Responsibly, respecting the author's rights
		Respecting the license protecting it
		Without citing sources/authors
	Nº 34. To prepare information I wish to upload to the Internet I make use of:	Citing sources/authors
		Draft pen and paper versions
		Drafts on electronic supports
		Classmates with whom I discuss what I am preparing
		Classmates who review what I am preparing before I publish it
		Teachers or experts who review what I have prepared
	Nº 32. When I want to generate new information for online publication:	I do not seek help. I edit and publish the information) directly
		I do not know how to do it.
		I publish it on a social network I use regularly.
		I use a specific tool (blog type)
	Nº 33. The digital contents I produce to share online are:	Depending on the type of information I use one tool or another (blog, social network, Googlesites, etc.)
		Text (wikis, blog)
		Iconic (photographs or imageses in flickr, instagram, etc.)
		Video (youtube, vimeo...)
Audio (podcast)		
Multimedia (slideshare, animoto, etc.)		
Hypermedia (Exelearning, websites in Wix or others)		
Nº 35. To prepare information I wish to upload to the Internet I make use of	Draft pen and paper versions	
	Drafts on electronic supports	
	Classmates with whom I discuss what I am preparing	
	Classmates who review what I am preparing before I publish it	
	Teachers or experts who review what I have prepared	
	I do not seek help. I edit and publish the information) directly	